

Synthesis of Possible Analgetic Agents

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A number of 1-alkyl-2-methyl-3-benzyl-3-carbethoxy pyrrolidines were prepared as possible analgetic agents by reductive ring closure of 3-carbethoxy-3-cyanomethyl-4-phenyl butan-2-one and subsequent alkylation. 1-Methyl derivative showed analgetic activity at a toxic dose level.

ALTHOUGH several attempts were made to correlate structure-activity relationship among analgetic agents, no definite conclusion could be drawn due to advent of analgetic agents of diverse structures.

Cavalla and co-workers¹, in 1961, observed high analgetic activity in some pyrrolidine compounds and since then pyrrolidine derivatives have received considerable attention as potential analgetic agents²⁻⁵. Present work describes the synthesis of a few pyrrolidines of the structure I, in which the same carbon contains both benzyl as well as carboxyethyl group.

I (R = H or alkyl)

II

3-Carbethoxy 3-cyanomethyl-4-phenyl butan-2-one (II) on hydrogenation in presence of Raney Nickel yielded 2-methyl-3-benzyl-3-carbethoxy pyrrolidine [I; R = H]. Alkylation with alkyl halide in the usual method produced desired N-alkylated compounds.

Pharmacology: Analgetic activity of these compounds in mice was kindly tested by Messrs. Bristol Laboratories, Syracuse, U.S.A., following hot plate method⁶. 1-Methyl derivative [I; R = CH₃] only showed analgetic activity at a dose of 150 mg/kg. body weight although symptoms of convulsions were observed at that dose.

Experimental

3-Carbethoxy-3-cyanomethyl-4-phenylbutane-2-one (II):

A solution of benzyl acetoacetic ester (28.5 g.; 0.13 mole) in dry benzene (50 ml) was added slowly to molecular sodium (2.3 g.; 0.1 mole) in dry benzene

(100 ml) under stirring. The mass was left overnight when the reaction was complete. Chloromethyl cyanide (7.6 g; 0.1 mole) in dry benzene (20 ml) was then added to the above sodio-derivative and refluxed for 14 hr. The reaction product was then poured into ice-cold water, extracted with benzene and the benzene layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The residual liquid after removal of benzene was distilled at 158°-60°/0.8 mm. Yield 10.5 g (41%). (Found: C, 69.2; H, 6.3; N, 5.3; C₁₅H₁₇O₃N requires C, 69.5, H, 6.6; N, 5.4%).

2-Methyl-3-benzyl-3-carbethoxy pyrrolidine (I; R = H)

The cyano compound II (20.6 g; 0.08 mole), dissolved in absolute alcohol, was reduced at 110° under 110 atoms with H₂ in presence of Raney Nickel Catalyst. The residual oil after removal of alcohol was treated with ice-cold dilute HCl and the neutral substance was removed by washing with ether. The clear acid extract was cooled and basified with ice-cold NaOH solution. The free amine separated out was extracted with ether and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The ether was removed and the residual amine was distilled from an oil bath at 118°-119°/0.3 mm. Yield 8 g (40-41%).

Hydrochloride, prepared by adding a solution of HCl gas in dry ether to the ethereal solution of the amine, was recrystallised from ethyl acetate; m.p. 176° (Data given in Table I). Picrate, m.p. 175.5°. (Found: N, 11.6. C₂₁H₂₄N₄O₉ requires N, 11.8%).

TABLE 1—1-ALKYL-2-METHYL-3-BENZYL-3-CARBETHOXY PYRROLIDINES (I)

No.	R	Alkylating reagent	b.p. of base °C (mm)	Yield %	m.p. °C of Hydrochloride	Formula (Hydrochloride)	Analysis ⁺					
							Found			Required		
						C%	H%	N%	C%	H%	N%	
1.	H	...	118-19(0.3)	40-41	176	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂ NCl	63.3	7.6	4.7	63.5	7.8	4.9
2.	CH ₃	Formic acid + formaldehyde	148-48(2.5)	49.0	122	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂ NCl	64.1	7.8	4.4	64.5	8.1	4.7
3.	C ₂ H ₅	Ethyl iodide	132-33(0.6)	48.5	129	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₂ NCl	65.2	8.1	4.3	65.5	8.3	4.5
4.	C ₃ H ₇	Propyl iodide	136-37(0.6)	57.8	138	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₂ NCl	66.1	8.3	4.2	66.4	8.6	4.3
5.	C ₄ H ₉	Butyl bromide	150(1.5)	49.5	141	C ₁₉ H ₃₀ O ₂ NCl	66.8	8.5	3.9	67.2	8.8	4.1

+ Hydrochlorides crystallised from ethyl acetate.

1,2-Dimethyl-3-benzyl-3-carbethoxy pyrrolidine (I; R = CH₃):

A mixture of compound (I; R = H; 1.7g; 0.007 mole), formic acid (98-100%; 1.8 g; 0.04 mole) and formaldehyde (37%; 1.5 ml; 0.02 mole) was heated on an oil bath for 14 hours at 95°-100°. Formic acid and formaldehyde were removed from an oil bath under reduced pressure. The residual mass was treated with NaOH solution and the amine was extracted out with ether. The ether layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The oil after removal of ether was distilled under reduced pressure; yield 0.9; g. b.p. 146°-48°/2.5 mm. Hydrochloride of the amine was recrystallised from acetate; m.p. 122° (Data given in Table 1).

1-Alkyl-2-methyl-3-benzyl-3-carbethoxy pyrrolidine (I; R = C₂H₅, n-C₃H₇ or n-C₄H₉):

Alkyl iodide or bromide (0.009 mole) was added to ice cold solution of the non-alkylated amine (0.006 mole) in benzene and the mixture was refluxed for 12-14 hr. Benzene and alkyl halide were removed from a water bath under reduced pressure. The residue was basified with NaOH solution and the liberated amine was extracted out with ether. The liquid residue after removal of solvent was distilled under vacuum.

Hydrochlorides of the above amines were recrystallised from ethyl acetate.

The physical properties and analytical data of the pyrrolidines are given in Table 1.

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